

UDC 656.073.7

AGRIS: D50

JEL classification: J88; K32; R51

A MODEL OF THE CONCEPT OF SIMPLIFIED CUSTOMS CLEARANCE OF PHYTOSANITARY GOODS

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МОДЕЛЬ КОНЦЕПЦИИ УПРОЩЕННОГО ТАМОЖЕННОГО ОФОРМЛЕНИЯ ФИТОСАНИТАРНЫХ ТОВАРОВ

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Abstract. Phytosanitary border-quarantine inspection is a type of non-tariff regulation that is used for importing or exporting goods on the territory of Georgia, to carry out other supervising or inspection procedures on them in accordance with the procedures provided for by law.

Goods of phytosanitary origin in the country's customs checkpoint are subject to the following procedures: the arrival of the goods at the phytosanitary inspection terminal, the arrival of vehicle, implementation of phytosanitary inspection (documentary inspection and stamping), issuing a new complete certificate, software processing of all documents by the logistics officer and their delivery to the information zone, where the documents will be handed over to the owner/customs declarator upon request. All of these customs procedures take some time.

Reforms were undertaken in recent years, which were implemented with a view to facilitating the customs clearance, have significantly reduced time spent on customs procedures.

Аннотация. Фитосанитарный пограничный карантинный контроль — это вид нетарифного регулирования, который используется для импорта или экспорта товаров с территории Грузии для осуществления других мер надзора и контроля в соответствии с процедурами, предусмотренными законодательством.

На таможенной границе страны грузы фитосанитарного происхождения подвергаются следующие процедуры: вхождение в терминал фитосанитарного контроля, представление транспортного средства, проведение фитосанитарного контроля (проверка сопутствующих документов), выпустить новый всеобъемлющий сертификат, материально-технический персонал выполнять занесение документов в соответствующей программе и передает их в информационную зону, где эти документы будут переданы владельцу/декларатору. Все эти таможенные процедуры требуют некоторого времени.

Реформы, осуществленные в последние годы, которые были реализованы с точки зрения облегчения таможенного оформления, значительно сократили время, затрачиваемое на таможенные процедуры.

Keywords: phytosanitary procedures, clearance time, transit cargo turnover.

Ключевые слова: фитосанитарные процедуры, время оформления, транзитный грузооборот.

Georgia imports large quantities of the produce of vegetable origin subject to phytosanitary inspection. Imports are growing every year, especially with regard to seasonality, mostly when particular types of goods are produced in insufficient quantities or not produced at all in the country.

Imported and exported goods of vegetable origin, which may contain the harmful organisms, or which even may be the hiding place for them, in compliance with legislation in force, are subject to phytosanitary border-quarantine inspection.

Phytosanitary border-quarantine inspection is a type of non-tariff regulation that is used for importing or exporting goods on the territory of Georgia, to carry out other supervising or inspection procedures on them in accordance with the procedures provided for by law.

The rule of the implementation of phytosanitary border-quarantine inspection defines the phytosanitary inspection procedures directed against the intrusion and spread of the harmful organisms containing in plants and plant products in the country. The phytosanitary rule has been developed by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), to ensure the principles and provisions of the International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC) adopted on 6 December 1951 by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), which also envisages the requirements of the EU legislation in this area [1]. The phytosanitary rule applies to the import, re-export, export and transit of goods specified by the Order No. 2-9 of January 18, 2008, of the Minister of Agriculture of Georgia "On approval of the list of products, materials and facilities subject to phytosanitary quarantine inspection", and it can also be applied to storage facilities, packaging, vehicles, containers and the other organisms, objects or materials, which may contain the harmful organisms, or which may be the hiding place for them [2]. The Legal Entity of Public Law - National Food Agency of the Ministry of Agriculture of Georgia, establishes the conditions of the importation of goods subject to phytosanitary inspection. The phytosanitary border-quarantine inspection is carried out by the Legal Entities of Public Law - Revenue Service and Customs Department of the Ministry of Finance of Georgia [2].

The documents to be presented at the economic border of Georgia for the implementation of phytosanitary border-quarantine inspection procedures are as follows:

- phytosanitary certification;
- pre-notification;
- permit for import of goods of vegetable origin subject to phytosanitary inspection, when required;

-other accompanying documentation provided for by law [1].

Goods earmarked for import in Georgia, at the border inspection checkpoint, are subject to:

- documentary verification;
- identity verification;
- health control;
- on-site sampling for the inspection or the laboratory analysis.

At the Georgian–Turkish border, particularly in the Sarpi Customs Checkpoint, which is one of the largest and most important crossing points in terms of both import and transit, upon arrival of the goods subject to phytosanitary inspection, the customs officer issues the simplified accounting certificate on a vehicle transporting the mentioned goods. Thereafter, the goods under customs supervision are moved to the Customs Clearance Zone (CCZ) “Batumi”, which is located near the border, and where phyto-vet sanitary inspection checkpoint is located, which structurally is a part of the Sarpi Customs Checkpoint.

When entering the CCZ “Batumi”, a vehicle loaded with the goods subject to phytosanitary inspection will be placed in the parking lot existing at the terminal, and the delivery driver hands over all necessary goods shipping documents to the customs officer. The customs officer provides software processing of these documents, and then they are handed over to phytosanitary inspector for further inspection.

When determining conformity between the documents and goods, as well as compliance with other requirements provided for by law, a person responsible for phytosanitary inspection gives a stamp of approval of these documents, which means that the goods are ready for including in commodity trade transactions. After that, these documents are returned to the customs officer who fills out completely the accounting certificate.

All these documents will be undergone software processing by the customs officer, and then, they will be sent for further processing. After that, the owner of goods, whom all these documents will be handed over to, by using the electronic order management system, goes to the operator, presents the documents and begins the clearance procedures. The duration of clearance, depending on the specificity of the item, is 15 minutes. Goods are included in commodity trade transactions and leave the CCZ “Batumi” terminal.

Goods of phytosanitary origin in the country’s customs checkpoint are subject to the following procedures: the arrival of the goods at the phytosanitary inspection terminal, the arrival of vehicle, implementation of phytosanitary inspection (documentary inspection and stamping), issuing a new complete certificate, software processing of all documents by the logistics officer and their delivery to the information zone, where the documents will be handed over to the owner/customs declarator upon request. All of these customs procedures take some time.

Reforms were undertaken in recent years, which were implemented with a view to facilitating the customs clearance, have significantly reduced time spent on customs procedures. At least 15 minutes are required for the clearance of goods. However, due to the specificity of goods, this time may be significantly increased. In addition, the owner standing in line may have to wait until the operator is free. This increases the time spent on customs clearance.

In order to reduce the duration of the clearance of goods subject to phytosanitary inspection, which is also reflected on the duration of the clearance of other goods, we consider it appropriate to undertake the following measures particularly:

1. There is a need for change in approach to the clearance of goods, and goods having one or more codes should be undergone the clearance simultaneously on-site, without transferring the documents to the clearance zone, that is, through the coordination with the functions of the CCZ.

2. There is a need for placing one or two operators in the facility owned by the Sarpi Customs Checkpoint existing on the territory of the CCZ

3. It is necessary to develop the software module, which will simplify the clearance of goods subject to phytosanitary inspection, by reflecting the basic information on goods, and, of course, by paying customs tariffs provided for by law.

As mentioned above, the customs clearance procedures are carried out in the CCZ. With the new approach, the goods, after phytosanitary inspection, without issuing the complete certificate,

should be undergone the clearance on-site. More specifically, after completion of the documentary verification, the above-mentioned documents should be handed over to the operators of the same facility, who will provide the clearance procedures in a simplified form, after their arrival at the green corridor, they will leave the clearance zone. This will significantly reduce the time on the clearance of goods and, in some cases, the expenses of the customs declarant as well since there are frequent cases when the owners have to pay twice because of the clearance outside their working hours.

This approach to the customs procedures will also reduce the time on the clearance of other goods, which will positively reflect on the movement of transit cargo and will facilitate the improvement of the quality of cargo traffic at the South Caucasus section of the Eurasian transport-logistics corridor.

Funding: This work was supported by Shota Rustaveli Georgian National Science Foundation (SRNSFG) [DP 2016_5. Organization and management of transport processes].

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*Работа поступила
в редакцию 20.06.2018 г.*

*Принята к публикации
24.06.2018 г.*

Cite as (APA):

Kochadze, T., Sharabidze, I., & Gudadze, A. (2018). A model of the concept of simplified customs clearance of phytosanitary goods. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 4(7), 357-360.

Ссылка для цитирования:

Kochadze T., Sharabidze I., Gudadze A. A model of the concept of simplified customs clearance of phytosanitary goods // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2018. Т. 4. №7. С. 357-360. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/kochadze-tp> (дата обращения 15.07.2018).